

A NEW VACUUM PRESSURE CASTING TECHNIQUE FOR FABRICATING NET-SHAPED FIBER REINFORCING METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A new vacuum pressure casting technique for fabricating fiber reinforcing metal matrix composites is presented in this paper. This process is somehow like a combination of vacuum infiltration and pressure casting. Without use of an autoclave, the infiltration between a carbon multifiber preform and molten alloy can be performed in vacuum under a high mechanical pressure. The infiltration length can reach to 250mm and the composite is net-shaped with well-distributed fibers. The tensile strength, bend strength and modulus of M40J/Al composite fabricated by this process are 574 MPa, 888.1 MPa and 158.6 GPa, respectively.

KEYWORDS: Vacuum pressure casting, M40J/Al, infiltration

INTRODUCTION

Researches on fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (FRM) have lasted for over 30 years. One of the most economical methods for fabricating FRM is a liquid infiltration into a fiber preform, such as squeeze casting and vacuum pressure infiltration.. Carbon or graphite fiber reinforcing aluminum composite is one of the most interesting FRM because carbon fiber has a lower price as continuous reinforcement. But there are three problems in fabricating carbon or graphite fiber reinforcing metal composite by a liquid method. Firstly, carbon fiber can not be wetted by molten aluminum until the melt temperature reaching to 1000 [1] and its diameter is very fine (less than 10 μ m) , so that high pressure is necessary to press the melt into a fiber preform. Secondly, carbon fiber can be oxidized at the temperature over 400 and react with aluminum above 500 . The higher the temperature is, the more severe the reaction is[2]. Therefore a lower infiltration temperature and a vacuum are very benefit to the composite properties. Finally, the number of a yarn of carbon fibers (3K, 6K, or 12K) is so large that it is very difficult to obtain a C_f/Al product with a well-distributed fiber, especially after a long distance infiltration. Furthermore it is very difficulties to fabricate a big sized or complicated shaped C_f/Al composite by those processes.

The main fabrication techniques of C_f/Al composite include vacuum infiltration under an inert pressure (referred as vacuum gas infiltration), squeeze casting and hot pressure of preform

wire. For vacuum gas infiltration, an inert gas is used as pressure application and a liquid infiltrates a fiber preform along its axial direction in the opposite direction of the applied pressure. An autoclave is needed in this process and the applied pressure can not be over 20MPa, so that it limits the shape and size of the fabricated composite [3]. For squeeze casting in which a ram of a press is used as the pressure application, an evacuation is difficult to carry out during the process and the fabricated composite is usually machined secondly. For hot pressure of preform wire, it has the advantage of higher strength reservation and good distribution of fibers. But the flexibility of the wire is too poor to fabricate a complicated structure. On the other hands, net-shaped process is needed because a secondary machining will decrease some composite properties obviously, for example the corrosion resistance of C_F/Al.

In this paper, a new process named as vacuum pressure casting is presented. A carbon preform is infiltrated by molten aluminum perfectly under a vacuum with a simple equipment. The composite is net-shaped and a trapezoidal shape C_F/Al composite which length is 250mm is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Experimental Materials

A type of carbon fiber (T300) and a type of graphite (M40J) fiber are used as reinforcements in this study. The diameter, tensile strength and modulus of T300 are 7μm, 3000 MPa and 277 GPa respectively, and the diameter, tensile strength and modulus of M40J are 5μm, 4.77 GPa and 377 GPa respectively. Aluminum alloy was used as matrix. Two shapes of preform are prepared. One is an rectangular preform with the sizes of 20×35×100mm and another one is a trapezoidal preform with the length of 250mm.

Composite Fabrication

The process procedure is schematically illustrated in Figure 1 .

Figure 1 The diagrammatic sketch of the process

The process used for composite fabrication may mainly be divided into fiber hybridization, preform preheating and infiltration with molten alloy. The fiber should be heated at 700 under a protection of N₂ for 10 sec. to remove its surface adhesive firstly, then hybridized with SiC_p which size is about 1μm. The preform is prepared by piling non-weft knitted fabric cloth obtained through winding hybridized fiber on a cylinder drove by an electric motor one up another. The number of layers is determined according to 50% fiber volume fraction in this study.

Analysis of Composite

The fabricated composite is investigated by optical microscopy. Tensile and bend testing are carried out using an electrical mechanical testing system. Rectangular-shaped samples are obtained by cutting the as-received composite parallel to the fiber's longitudinal axis. The width and height of the sample are 10 mm and 2 mm respectively. The gauge lengths for tensile and bend tests are 50 mm and 40 mm respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design of Vacuum Pressure Casting Die

As mentioned above, the carbon fiber has a small diameter, poor oxide resistance and bad wettability with aluminum. To ensure the infiltration between the fiber and the matrix and to get a near net shaped C_F/Al composite, the casting die should satisfy the following conditions:

- The preform should be infiltrated by a liquid in a set of dies which cavity size is equal to the size of the product.
- The cavity of die can be evacuated to eliminate the backpressure (existed in squeeze casting) and protect the fiber from oxidation.
- A high pressure can be provided to ensure the molten alloy infiltrating into a bigger preform.

According to those, the designed die in this study for preparing FRM composites is schematically illustrated in Figure 2 .

Figure 2 Apparatus of the process

The principle of this process is somehow like the combination of vacuum infiltration and pressure casting. We name it as vacuum pressure casting. A ram of a press is used for the pressure application and the pressure in the mould cavity can reach as higher as that in squeeze casting. The main characteristics of this apparatus are that the melting and casting of aluminum is done in air while the infiltration is carried out in vacuum. The sealant in the sprue gate is either strong enough to ensure the preform evacuation or ease to be broken at the moment of pressing the melt into the cavity by the ram. By application of this technology, the equipment is simpler than that of vacuum gas pressure because the autoclave is not needed while the infiltration is similar to that of squeeze casting.

Analysis of Infiltration Process

By vacuum squeeze casting process, both preforms are infiltrated by aluminum perfectly. Although a infiltration length of a process is related with the preheated temperature of preform the casting temperature of alloy and applied pressure, the infiltration length of this process is larger than that of the vacuum gas infiltration, which is about 100 mm reported in reference [3]. The size of the as-received composite is equal to the designed size. It means that a near net shaped composite can be fabricated when the size of the designed inner die equal to the sizes of the product.

During the process of casting, a tight fit between the chamber and the inner die is necessary for establishing enough pressure in the mould cavity, so the chamber and its charge are pressed under a certain pressure before the molten is put into the chamber. The mechanical pressure reaches to 100-150 MPa during the infiltration applied through the ram.

Hybridization of SiC_p into fibers is very important to ensure the total preform infiltrated by aluminum perfectly. Hybridization can separate fibers from contacting with each other and enlarge the distance between fibers, then decrease the infiltration resistance and increase the infiltration length. When the preform is not hybridized and there are a lot of uninfiltreated spots existing in the composite.

It is found that the direction of applied pressure has an important effect on the infiltration. When the applied pressure is perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of fibers, the preform will be pressed closely before infiltration, so the resistance of infiltration will become larger. But a longitudinal infiltration may cause the moving and winding of fibers, which are discussed in following.

Observation of Optical Microscopy

Figure 3 shows the optical microphotograph of a polished C_F/Al composites. Because the molten aluminum infiltrates along the axis of fiber in this process, some longitudinal pressure is put on the preform. The pressure is caused by the crash of molten aluminum when it is pushed into the die and the friction between fiber and molten aluminum during the infiltration. The friction increases with the increase of the infiltration length. If the pressure is higher than the compress strength of the preform, the fiber will move down, as shown in (a) where the fiber are

(a) longitudinal section without binder (b) longitudinal section with binder (c) cross section

Figure 3 Optical microphotography of C_F/Al

decrease the descending speed of the ram and improve the compress strength of the preform by adding some acid phosphate binder[4]. then the distribution of the fibers in its longitudinal direction can be improved significantly and the fibers are neat and paralleled, as shown in (b).

Fig(c) illustrates the crass section of the composite. It is found that the fiber distributes in the matrix uniformly with no uninfiltreated spots in it.

Mechanical Properties

Table 1 shows the testing results.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of C_F/Al composite

Properties	Tensile strength MPa	Young's modulus GPa	Bend strength MPa
Average	574	158.6	888.1
S.D [*]	26.8	1.76	28.7

* standard deviation

The tested tensile strength is much lower than the calculated value by ROM. By testing the strength of mono fiber extracted from as-received composite using 20% NaOH solution, it is found that the degradation of M40J fiber is about 26% during the process. Result of X-ray diffraction of the extracted fiber shows that there is Al₄C₃ existed in its surface. It can be concluded that the fiber has reacted with aluminum during the infiltration.

CONCLUSION

- (1) The vacuum squeeze casting process has the advantage of squeeze casting and vacuum gas infiltration and a near net shaped composite can be obtained.
- (2) The infiltration length of C_F/Al composite can larger than 250mm and the distribution of fiber is quit well after adding acid phosphate binder and adjusting the descending speed of the ram.
- (3) The tensile strength, Young's modulus and bend strength of C_F/Al composite are 574 MPa, 158 GPa and 888 MPa respectively.

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